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Case Study Article

Analysis of Bioactive Compounds in Indigenous Mushrooms for Neurodegenerative Treatments

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ABSTRACT

Antiphospholipid antibody syndrome (APS) is an autoimmune disorder characterized by the persistently elevated levels of antiphospholipid antibodies (aPL) and is associated with recurrent thromboembolic events and complications in pregnancy. To diagnose definite APS, the classification criteria require at least one clinical criterion (either thrombosis or pregnancy complications) to be present, along with one laboratory criterion, which includes the presence of lupus anticoagulant (LAC), anticardiolipin (aCL) antibodies, or anti- β 2-glycoprotein I (a β 2GPI) antibodies on two or more separate occasions, at least 12 weeks apart. Additionally, thrombosis must be confirmed using objective, validated diagnostic methods. In this report, a patient of 27-year-old female with multiple headache attacks and thrombotic events, was evaluated for APS secondary to stroke. The patient was managed with anticoagulation therapy and remained clinically stable following intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Antiphospholipid syndrome is an autoimmune clotting disorder characterized by the presence of antiphospholipid antibodies in the setting of thrombosis or systemic lupus erythematosus, pregnancy loss or other complications. The syndrome is diagnosed with clinical and laboratory criteria.^[1] Many, but not all, lupus anticoagulant

patients also have elevated levels of IgG or IgM antiphospholipid antibodies. The prevalence of the syndrome in the general population is low and only a small percentage of patients diagnosed with thrombosis have a phospholipid circulating in their blood.^[3] The typical age of onset for primary APS is between 35 and 40 years, and the condition is more prevalent in women than men. The clinical

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manifestations of the syndrome include venous and arterial thrombosis and embolism, disseminated large and small vessel thrombosis with accompanying multi organ ischemia and infarction, stroke, premature coronary artery disease, and spontaneous pregnancy losses. In the early 1950s, the development of the partial thromboplastin time coagulation test, which used a phospholipid extract of animal brain (cephalin)

as a platelet equivalent to accelerate coagulation, led to the recognition of an anticoagulant activity in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus frequently accompanied by BFP (Biologic false positive) - syphilis tests.^[2] This phenomenon, named the “lupus anticoagulant”. The diagnosis of antiphospholipid syndrome requires any of the following clinical and laboratory criteria (Table 1)^[8]

Table 1: Criteria For Antiphospholipid Antibody Syndrome^[4]

◆ Clinical Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venous, arterial, or small-vessel Thrombosis in any organ. • One or more foetal losses with normal foetal morphologic characteristics, Unexplained, and after 10 weeks of gestation. • One or more premature births at or before 34 weeks gestation due to severe preeclampsia, eclampsia, or placental insufficiency. • Three or more recurrent foetal losses before 10 weeks of gestation.
◆ Laboratory Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium to high levels of IgG and IgM antiphospholipid antibodies (>40 GPL or MPL) or above the 99th percentile on 2 occasions at least 12 weeks apart with ELISA. • IgG/IgM anti-β₂ glycoprotein-1 antibodies at a titre above the 99th percentile on 2 or more occasions at least 12 weeks apart with ELISA. • Lupus anticoagulant with dilute Russel viper venom time and a PTT, followed by a mixing study and confirmatory testing on 2 occasions 12 weeks apart.

Figure 1: Other Manifestations That Are Associated With APS^[1]

Catastrophic APS refers to development of thrombosis in 3 or more organ systems with positive results for antiphospholipid antibodies or lupus anticoagulant, or both, in a short time, such as a week. Life-threatening organ ischemia often occurs in the CNS and pulmonary, renal, gastrointestinal tract, and cardiac systems.^[5] In cases of catastrophic antiphospholipid syndrome (APS), patients may present with symptoms such as acute pulmonary haemorrhage, confusion, severe abdominal pain from bowel infarction, and kidney failure necessitating dialysis, depending on the severity and organs involved. These patients require care in a critical care settings. The prognosis is generally poor, and treatment often includes multiple courses of plasma exchange, high-dose corticosteroids, and anticoagulation therapy.^[5]

The initial approach to APS treatment involves use of unfractionated heparin or low-molecular-weight heparin (LMWH) in combination with warfarin for 3 to 5 days until the warfarin reaches a therapeutic effect, with an increased international normalized ratio (INR) of 2 to 3. For most patients with definite APS and thrombosis, warfarin will need to be taken indefinitely. For pregnant women with definite APS, subcutaneous LMWH is used; warfarin is resumed in the postpartum period.^[6] For pregnant women with definite APS and a history of prior pregnancy morbidity, low-dose aspirin and LMWH are used in combination.^[7] Patients with either antiphospholipid antibodies or lupus anticoagulant should not receive oestrogen-containing oral contraceptive pills, since these patients may be at higher risk for thrombosis. For patients who have recurrent thrombosis despite warfarin treatment and an INR of 2 to 3, additional intensive therapy

is suggested, such as an increase in target INR ranges from 3 to 4 and the addition of LMWH and low-dose aspirin therapy.^[9] Monitoring the INR in patients with antiphospholipid syndrome (APS) can be challenging due to the potential interference of anti-prothrombin antibodies, which can falsely extend the prothrombin time even in the absence of warfarin therapy or lupus anticoagulant, thereby raising the INR. A possible alternative is to monitor factor Xa levels.^[10]

Case Report:

A 27-year-old female of weight 75 kgs, height 5 feet 6 inches, and BMI of 29 kg/m² with no known drug allergies presented to our hospital with a history of daily headaches for the past year and one episode of tonic seizures- 12 days back. She had a recent history of weakness of the left upper and lower limb with loss of speech which recovered after a few hours and also a recent history of a right MCA- territory stroke due to right M1 occlusion for which she was evaluated at a local hospital where the patient was treated with DIVALGRESS ER 250 (Divalproex) for CNS vasculitis and referred to this hospital for further workup and management. Upon admission, the patient was conscious, coherent and revealed a left upper limb pronator drift, mild left hemisensory loss and no motor deficits. The routine laboratory test complete blood count [CBC] was performed which revealed Hb-14.0g/dl, Eosinophils-0.1%, MCV 83.0 fl, platelets- 3.84×10³/mm³, Absolute monocyte count-1.41×10³/mm³, Absolute lymphocyte count-3.47×10³/mm³, Absolute Neutrophil count-19.02×10³/mm³, Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) was 5.54 mm/hr and serum creatinine- 0.61 mg/dL. Other laboratory investigations mentioned in the tables 2,3,4,5.

Table 2: Anti-Nuclear Antibodies -IgG

Dilution	Evaluation Grade	Interpretation
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1:100	Negative	No specific antibodies detected
1:100	Weak positive+	Low level of Antibodies detected
1:100	Positive++	Moderate level of antibodies detected
1:100	Positive +++	Significant level of antibodies detected
1:130	Strong positive	High level of Antibodies detected

Category	Detected levels	Result	Normal levels
Anti-Cardiolipin Screen IgA + G + M	2.7 Ratio	Positive	Ratio < 1.0
Anti-Cardiolipin Antibodies-IgG	03 -IgG-U/ml	Negative	< 12 PL-IgG-U/ml
Anti-Cardiolipin Antibodies-IgM	27 IgM-U/ml	Positive	< 12 PL-IgM-U/ml
Anti-Beta 2-Glyco Protein IgG (Anti Apolipoprotein H)	03 RU/ml	Negative	< 20 RU/ml

Test Reference	Result	Biological
(d RVVT)	Negative	28-45 sec
LA Screening Time	30.3	28-40 sec
LA Confirm Time	28.2	< 1.3: Normal
Ratio	1.07	1.5-1.8: Moderate LA
		1.8-2.4: High LA
		>2.4: Very High LA
		1.3-1.4: Borderline +ve
		Advised Mixing studies

ELISA Tests	Value	Reference Value
Anti-Proteinase 3-IgG (PR3/c ANCA)	-	-
Anti-Myeloperoxidase-IgG (MPO/p ANCA)	-	-
Immunofluorescence Dilution		
1:20		No specific antibodies detected
1:20		Low level of Antibodies detected
1:20		Moderate level of Antibodies detected

1:20		Significant level of Antibodies detected
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3T MRI brain with vessel wall imaging did not show any features of vessel wall enhancement but revealed a tuft of arterioles in the right MCA region, suggestive of secondary Moyamoya disease. A 2D echocardiogram showed good left ventricular function with no regional wall motion abnormalities. As part of the young stroke work-up, investigations for autoimmune and procoagulant conditions were done. ANA, ANCA,

and APLA work-ups were performed, and APLA with anti-cardiolipin IgM was found to be positive. Based on the physical and considering objective evidence, patient was diagnosed with Anti Phospholipid Antibody Syndrome (APS). Patient was treated with these medications during hospitalisation mentioned in the Table 6.

Management:

Table 6: ROA (Route of Administration); PO- Per Oral; OD- Omni die (once daily); BD- Bis die (twice daily), HS-Hora somni (at bedtime); APD (Acid Peptic Disorder); APS (Antiphospholipid antibody syndrome); CVA (Cerebrovascular Accident).

Medication	Dose	Route	Frequency	Indication
Rosloy gold	20/75/75mg	OD	CVA	
Divalgress ER	250mg	PO	BD	Headache
Neksium	40mg	PO	OD	APD Prophylaxis
Ultracet	1 tab	PO	BD	Pain
Topamac	25mg	PO	H/S	Headache
Tryptomer	10mg	PO	H/S	Headache
Abaxis	5mg	PO	BD	APS
Ecosprin	75mg	PO	OD	APS

DISCUSSION:

In this report, we described a rare case of an adult female who presented with a history of daily headaches for the past year and episodes of tonic seizures 12 days back. She had a recent history of weakness of the left upper and lower limb with loss of speech which recovered after a few hours and also a recent history of a right MCA- territory stroke due to right M1 occlusion. The physician advised investigations of ANA, ANCA, and APLA which revealed APLA with anti-cardiolipin

IgM was positive. Based on the objective evidence & clinical condition of the patient, she was diagnosed with Anti Phospholipid Antibody Syndrome (APS) and treated accordingly. The patient was discharged with these medications (Table 7). The patient and her caretaker were advised on how to proceed with the treatment, and the patient was counseled about drug adherence.

Discharge Medications:

Table 7: ROA (Route of Administration); PO- Per Oral; OD- Omni die (once daily); BD- Bis die (twice daily); APS (Anti phospholipid antibody syndrome); CVA (Cerebrovascular Accident).

Medication	Dose	Frequency	ROA	Duration	Indication
Eliquis (Apixaban)	5mg	BD	PO	1-month	APS
Ecosprin (Aspirin+Glycine)	75mg	OD	PO	1-month	CVA

Tryptomer (Amitriptylline)	10mg	OD	PO	1-month	Headache
Topamac (Topiramate)	25mg	OD	PO	1-month	Headache
Topamac Topiramate	50mg	OD	PO	1-month	Headache (To be started after a week)

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